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“Competence Areas” as a New Notion Instead of Teacher Competencies

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Abstract

The concept of "teacher competence" has been used as a defining concept in explaining the competence levels of teachers in different fields since the early 2000s. However, with the publication of the 2019 Turkish course curriculum, it was seen that this concept was not included in the program, but instead "competence areas" were explained in detail. In this context, the study aimed to evaluate the 2019 Turkish Lesson Curriculum in terms of teacher competencies. Before the publication of the curriculum 2019, primary teaching competencies in the literature were investigated and listed, and the Turkish lesson curriculum was then evaluated considering those teacher competencies. In the 2019 Turkish Lesson Curriculum, unlike other programs, the scope and content of competency areas were defined in detail. Thus, the analysis of competency areas by teacher competence contributes to the literature. In the literature, teacher competencies were associated with various skills such as "digital competence," "learning to learn," "social and civic competencies" and "the sense of initiative and entrepreneurship." The 2019 Turkish Lesson Curriculum was assessed considering those skills. Accordingly, in the Turkish Lesson Curriculum 2019, the most critical competence area is the "digital competence" dimension. We can see the reflections of digital competence in the definition of skills and educational text types. The precondition for fostering digital competence in students is that teachers have digital competence. Thus, it is suggested to redefine and determine teaching competencies, knowledge, and skills related to "digital competence."

Keywords: Competence Areas, Teacher Competence, Curriculum, Turkish Lesson

1. Introduction

1.1. Teacher Competence

The concept of teacher competence is characterized by educational process capability. In this sense, teachers are expected to possess additional competencies apart from evaluating educational activities. Instead, it is also vital to design, plan, and implement the activities and monitor the educational process. Lastly, the capacity to choose

an appropriate assessment and evaluation method is critical for the evaluation phase. In a review of national and international literature on teaching competence, it can be seen that teachers' qualifications include as follows:

According to The Council for Accreditation of Teacher Education (CATE) in England, the teacher competencies are categorized under six field: curriculum knowledge, planning, classroom management, assessment and evaluation, self-assessment, professional relations, and qualifications (Moore, 1996 cited in Coşkun, et al., 2010: 38). The Turkish Ministry of Education described teachers' professional qualifications in two main dimensions: professional competence and general competence. General competence includes personal and professional values, student, teacher, and learning setting dimensions, monitoring and evaluating the learning outcomes, and relations with society, school, and family. Professional competence involves issues surrounding educational development, monitoring, assessment procedures, personal and professional qualifications, art and aesthetics, language skills, scientific and technological development, personal responsibilities and socialization, and physical education, and security (Coşkun, et al., 2010: 381).

Teacher competencies embrace the characteristics such as knowledge, skills, attitudes, values, and behaviors that teachers are expected to have. In general, teaching competencies are discussed under three main headings: subject matter knowledge, professional knowledge, and general knowledge (Şişman, 2009: 68).

The teacher competencies and qualifications described in the reports of the Bologna Process for the countries in the European Union are as follows (the Commission of the European Communities, cited in 2007. Şişman, 2009: 70):

A High-Quality Profession: Teachers should be trained in higher education institutions, have a broad knowledge of the subject matter, excellent pedagogical knowledge, and recognize social and cultural dimensions of education.

A Profession of Teachers with Lifelong Learning: Teachers should appreciate the importance of learning and applying new knowledge and be promoted to improve professional careers.

A Mobile Profession: Mobility is the central concept for teacher education programs. Teachers should be encouraged to cooperate with colleagues from other European countries.

A Cooperative Profession: Teacher education institutions should cooperate with schools, and the training should also be carried out with regional business networks and stakeholders."

Communication is vital for the teaching profession. The target audience is human, so teachers should be willing to teach and have positive attitudes towards the profession. Besides, it is crucial to meet the age requirements professionally and follow the current developments. In this respect, faith in self-efficacy also plays a role in loving and improving the profession.

Teachers take an active role in competently educating students in line with the requirement of the age. Positive attitudes towards the profession and affective competencies are among the fundamental features that teachers should have to improve the education. The reasons for choosing the teaching profession, the teaching perceptions, and formal education affect their opinions about the profession. Teacher candidates' motivation depends on developing positive perspectives on the teaching profession (Karadağ, 2012: 46).

Strong self-efficacy beliefs suggest that they would show more effort to become an ideal teacher. Therefore, teacher training programs should include practices strengthening teacher candidates' self-efficacy beliefs (Azar, 2010: 247).

Teachers' perceptions also influence students' confidence in the teacher and role modeling. Thus, teachers must first believe in themselves to convince students to trust their knowledge and guidance. Teachers are role models for students in establishing an identity Teachers' feelings of efficacy are directly associated with children's motivation to learn (Sünbül, 1996: 602,604). Teacher candidates should also have certain personality traits. Teachers who have unfavorable attitudes towards the teaching profession and students in the classroom reflect them to the students (Kılıç, as cited in 1997. Çetinkaya, 2007: 9).

In his studies on self-efficacy, Bandura (1977; 1982; as cited in 1986. Aksoy & Diken, 2009: 711) stated that individuals tend to avoid situations that they think they cannot cope with self-efficacy perceptions directly affect their efforts to solve a problem.

An essential factor that should be dealt with in increasing the teaching profession's quality is teacher candidates' stress in the teaching certification exam. The majority of teacher candidates experience the anxiety of not being appointed/employed even when they attend the faculty.

In Turkey, teacher recruitment has become more challenging than attending a teaching department at a university. There are many unemployed teacher candidates- more than needed. Therefore, teacher candidates study very hard for the recruitment exam and are under stress and pressure (Arı & Yılmaz, 2015: 923).

In their study, Ayrancı (2007: 69) attempted to describe Turkish lesson teacher candidates' general knowledge level by using a survey. The survey was completed by students, parents, and school principals and aimed to reveal their expectations from Turkish lesson teachers. The study showed that Turkish lesson teacher candidates did not follow professional publications, were not a member of any social club, did not know about others' expectation from them, were incompetent in using educational materials, did not have qualified practical training, and wanted to replace specific lessons with other lessons that they believe to be more useful in the classroom. The participant Turkish teacher candidates got a medium score in the field knowledge test, which is very insufficient for such an important profession. They also got an average score on the placement test related to educational practices. It was even below the required score for the Public Personnel Selection Examination (PPSE). It was concluded that the Turkish lesson teacher candidates were incompetent in educational sciences.

Teachers should have pedagogical knowledge, professional formation, and general knowledge. As the researchers found a direct relationship between school achievement and language skills, Turkish teachers play a fundamental role in education (Çetinkaya, 2007: 5).

1.2. The Choice of Teaching Profession

Internal and external factors can be influential in choosing teaching as a profession. When internal factors are determinants in choosing the teaching profession, it stands for that those individuals also have the necessary professional and personality traits. Professional commitment is also widespread among those who choose the teaching profession for the sake of society.

The literature findings of the reasons for professional career choice provide essential information in planning the professional training, monitoring its effectiveness, and predicting future professional outcomes (Çermik, et al., 2017: 643).

The reasons for professional career choices can be discussed under the three groups: internal, external, and altruistic reasons. Career choices should be primarily based on internal reasons as they are characterized by "loving to teach" or "showing interest in a particular field." In its simplest form, external reasons refer to indirect professional qualifications (Kyriacou & Coulthard, cited in 2000. Çermik, et al., 2017: 644). Lastly, altruistic reasons represent the beliefs related to the social benefits of being a teacher and contributing to children and society. As stated above, external, utilitarian, and stereotypical reasons lead to professional commitment problems in the long term (Çermik, et al., 2017: 645).

It is suggested that teacher candidates should read the curriculum in detail before the recruitment. Researches show that teacher qualifications are still questioned. The sympathy to the profession also affects professional attitudes. These problems can be overcome by improving the professional conditions and ensuring that volunteer and qualified people become teachers.

According to Çetinkaya (2007: 53), students who are not satisfied with their department do not feel ready for the profession. They also do not have positive attitudes about the teaching profession.

Despite the high number of new education faculties, there are still lacks in specific teacher training programs. Thus, authorities attempt to fill the gap by delivering certificate programs and distance education. They sometimes recruit university graduates as teachers, which is still a contradictory discussion regarding the teacher qualifications (Şişman, 2009: 79).

Recruitment of competent teacher candidates is as important as teacher training programs. Teacher candidates' opinions about the teaching profession provide essential benefits to organize education. The teaching profession is closely related to the teacher candidates' thoughts and behaviors (Özbek, et al., 2007: 222).

The economic and social regulations and improvements can promote positive attitudes towards the profession among teacher candidates (Özbek, et al., 2007: 232).

In their study, Şimşek and Büyükkıdık (2015: 37) investigated teachers' regrets and found that only five teachers mentioned no regrets in their lives, which implies that many teachers have regrets in life. Those teachers wanted the opportunity to go back to change some negative experiences, have better financial status, and retire at a later age. Three teachers emphasized that they had wished to be recruited where they wanted to work before retirement, which shows teachers' complaints about being unable to work where they wanted. It seems that it also affected their retirement lives. Only one teacher was pessimistic about what he did. However, most of the participant teachers felt good as they provided a promising future for their children, they became a teacher, had a happy family, continued working, and had social security benefits. Indeed, having a happy family life, promising future for children, and social security benefits were among the primary concerns of the participant teachers (Şimşek & Büyükkıdık, 2015: 37).

Positive attitudes towards the teaching profession can be assumed as a condition of being a qualified teacher. Teachers substantially contribute to the national development through their raising competent and talented students. Thus, it is vital to determine students' characteristics and skills early and guide them to appropriate professions (Göktaş, 2017: 1293).

In his study, Şahin (2011: 1177) found that due to the economic and social class-related problems, some participants had to study in a field and work where they did not want to for a permanent job, and they felt obliged to work as a teacher for a living. However, despite those unfavorable conditions, they felt disappointed when they were not appointed to teaching positions. He believes that those unemployed teacher candidates would experience profound economic and psychological problems.

1.3 The Importance of the Research

The concept of teacher competence has been investigated since the early 2000s, and there are many studies on this topic (Kiraz, 2003; Kocasaraç, 2003; Aktağ & Walter, 2005; Kahyaoğlu & Yangın, 2007; Karadağ, 2007; Çetinkaya, 2007; Karacaoğlu, 2008; Şişman, 2009). Some researchers examined the relationships between teaching competence and effective teaching dimensions (Kızıltepe, 2002; Şen & Erişen, 2002; Karakelle, 2005; Dilekmen, 2008, Şahin, 2011; Özkan & Arslantaş, 2013). Others concentrate on its relationship with Turkish lesson teaching competencies" (Özlük, 2010; Yılmaz, 2010; Maltepe, 2011; Şengül, 2012). However, in the 2019 Turkish Lesson Curriculum, unlike other programs, the scope and content of competency areas were defined in detail. Thus, the analysis of competency areas by teacher competence contributes to the literature.

1.4. The Purpose of the Research

The research aimed to evaluate the 2019 Turkish Lesson Curriculum by teacher competencies. Before the publication of the curriculum 2019, primary teaching competencies in the literature were investigated, and the Turkish lesson curriculum was reviewed considering teacher competencies.

2. Method

The Method section describes in detail how the study was conducted, including conceptual and operational definitions of the variables used in the study, Different types of studies will rely on different methodologies; however, a complete description of the methods used enables the reader to evaluate the appropriateness of your methods and the reliability and the validity of your results, It also permits experienced investigators to replicate the study, If your manuscript is an update of an ongoing or earlier study and the method has been published in detail elsewhere, you may refer the reader to that source and simply give a brief synopsis of the method in this section.

2.1 Research Pattern

This study, which examines the relationship between the concept of teacher competence with the concepts of "The Dimensions of Effective Teaching," "Special Field Competencies for Turkish Lesson Teachers" and evaluated through the competency areas in 2019 Turkish Lesson Curriculum, was carried out with a basic qualitative research design. Basic qualitative research is one of the most common research methods used in education, which can be seen in all discipline and practice areas. In this research method, the data; It is collected through observation, interview or document review (Merriam, 2002).

2.2 Study Material and Collection of Data

In this study, the 2019 Turkish Lesson Curriculum was used as the study material. In this context in collecting of data, eight competence areas under the heading "Competencies" were examined and evaluated. In addition, the basic approach of the curriculum, subject and theme examples, and text types were examined and evaluated in terms of "teacher competence." Turkish Lesson Curriculum has been chosen as the study material because it is the most basic reference resource for Turkish lesson teachers, teacher candidates and the relevant academicians.

Figure 1: Study Material of the Study and the Subheadings

2.3 Analysis of Data

In the study, document analysis method was used. Document review is a systematic process, including assessing both printed and electronic materials (Bowen, 2009). It is characterized by describing, categorizing, researching, and interpreting the materials (Payne & Payne, 2004: 60). It can also be defined as collecting, reviewing, and analyzing various documents as the primary source of research data (O'leary: 2004). In a study, it can be used as the only research method or applied with other qualitative methods (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2008: 187).

The method covers the analysis of written materials about the target phenomenon or facts and is an advantageous data collection technique for almost any research. There are several steps in reviewing a document, but they should be considered as general guidelines. Researchers can reinterpret and manipulate those stages depending on their research problem and the type, content, and depth of the data they aim to obtain (Yenilmez & Sölpük, 2014: 35). Document analysis is also known as documentary scanning or documentary observation. Document analysis method can be used for two different purposes; general scanning and content analysis. It refers to the systematic analysis of the records or documents as a data source. A prerequisite for successful document analysis is to find, review, and synthesize the target documents to reach a particular result and opinion (Karasar, 2007).

Document analysis is a systematic procedure for reviewing or evaluating documents—both printed and electronic (computer-based and Internet-transmitted) material. Like other analytical methods in qualitative research, document analysis requires that data be examined and interpreted in order to elicit meaning, gain understanding, and develop empirical knowledge (Corbin & Strauss, 2008). O'Leary (2017) explains document analysis as a research tool that aims to collect, study, question and analyze various written text formats as the primary research data source.

Bowen (2009: 31) express the advantages of using document analysis method as follows:

- **Efficient method:** Document analysis is less time-consuming and therefore more efficient than other research methods. It requires data selection, instead of data collection.
- **Availability:** Many documents are in the public domain, especially since the advent of the Internet, and are obtainable without the authors' permission. This makes document analysis an attractive option for qualitative researchers.
- **Cost-effectiveness:** Document analysis is less costly than other research methods and is often the method of choice when the collection of new data is not feasible. The data (contained in documents) have already been gathered; what remains is for the content and quality of the documents to be evaluated.
- **Lack of obtrusiveness and reactivity:** Documents are 'unobtrusive' and 'non-reactive'—that is, they are unaffected by the research process. Therefore, document analysis counters the concerns related to reflexivity (or the lack of it) inherent in other qualitative research methods.
- **Stability:** As a corollary to being non-reactive, documents are stable.

Figure 2: Advantages of Using Document Analysis Method

In document analysis, current documents and document management practices are studied and described, and new document structures and document management practices are developed. Document analysis is thus

regarded as a means for document design; it is an iterative process producing in its initial stages definitions for old document structures and later on definitions for new document structures (Salminen, Kauppinen & Lehtovaara, 1997).

4. Findings

This section covers the "Dimensions of Effective Teaching," "Special Field Competencies for Turkish Lesson Teachers," and "Competence Areas in the 2019 Turkish Lesson Curriculum".

4.1 The Dimensions of Effective Teaching

According to Karakelle (2005: 3-4), effective teaching dimensions are as follows:

a. Professional Knowledge

The knowledge of various aspects of the profession can be considered as a standard dimension. The professional competence, knowledge of teaching techniques and students' developmental characteristics, and the learning process are among the basic knowledge needs of an effective teacher.

b. Teaching Skills

Another standard dimension includes the skills and competencies related to the teaching process. An effective teacher should have a rich repertoire of teaching techniques, apply them considering the subject topic and students' academic readiness, and enrich the educational process.

c. Student Relationships

Almost all researches stress the importance of behavior and communication style with the student. Influential teachers are friendly, and can properly communicate with students, appreciate and support their individuality.

d. Presentation Skills

The presentation skills include using influential voice, gestures, mimicry, organizing the lesson, and making clear and precise presentations.

e. Classroom Management

Classroom management is characterized by making the necessary arrangements to create an efficient learning environment and a warm atmosphere in the classroom. Many studies have shown that effective teachers are competent in classroom management and create a productive and festive classroom atmosphere.

f. Personal Traits and Attitudes

An effective teacher should be flexible, enthusiastic, and cooperative. They should think multidimensionally, behave friendly, and believe in lifelong learning.

4.2 Special Field Competencies for Turkish Lesson Teachers

Teachers are required to have some competencies in many fields in order to develop the knowledge, skills, attitudes and values that their students need and to perform their teaching profession well (Can, 2019: 1621). Teachers should have sufficient knowledge, skills and qualifications in order to play their leading roles in training students according to their needs. In order to meet these needs, teachers should know the special field competencies. Competence fields are shown in Figure 3:

Figure 3: Special Field Competencies for Teachers

Considering the information presented in Figure 3, it can be stated that professional knowledge includes knowledge about facts, principles, processes and general concepts related to the teaching profession. Professional skills include the cognitive and practical skills necessary for successful performance in the teaching profession. Professional qualification consists of personal characteristics, qualifications, attitudes, values and responsibilities attributed to the teaching profession. These three competency dimensions are designed to complement each other in order to have a manageable number of qualifications in terms of scope and not to consist of overlapping and repetitive expressions. Among these dimensions, the 'skills' dimension includes the knowledge - field knowledge, pedagogy knowledge, vocational knowledge, general culture - group. In this sense, teachers are expected to have information about the sub-competency groups included in the skill dimension "learning environments, planning teaching, teaching methods and techniques and evaluation" (Buldu, 2014: 205).

Figure 4: Levels Based on the Primary Education Curriculum

The Turkish Ministry of National Education (MoNE) published its report on general teacher competence criteria and particular field competencies in 2008 (Temizyürek & Aksoy, 2016: 104). One of the competency areas was published as Turkish Lesson Teachers' Special Field Competencies (MoNE, 2008). Based on the primary education curriculum, each competency area is represented by A1, A2, and A3.

A1 Level: It includes performance indicators regarding teachers' curriculum practices and professional knowledge, skills, and attitudes.

A2 Level: The performance indicators show that teachers proficiently fulfill the curriculum requirements, diversify the educational practices, and consider students' interests and needs, as well as the knowledge and awareness at the A1 level.

A3 Level: It includes performance indicators that require the teacher to diversify and enrich the A2 level practices, taking into account the different teaching variables. A3 level teachers create unique practices and cooperate with colleagues, parents, non-governmental organizations, and other institutions (<https://oygm.MEB.gov.tr/www/ilkogretim-ozel-alan-yeterlilikleri/icerik/257>).

The competencies and performance indicators related to the *Turkish Lesson Teacher Special Field Competence* are as follows:

Figure 5: Turkish Lesson Teacher Special Field Competencies and Performance Indicators

As seen in the information presented in Figure 5, there are five competencies and performance indicators:

1. *Planning and Organization* includes planning the teaching process, organizing the learning setting, preparing materials, and using resources. There are four competence components and 19 performance indicators in this area.

2. *Language Skills Development* refers to organizing activities to improve students' comprehension and expressive skills and promote the correct and effective use of Turkish by considering students' needs, national values, and Atatürk's views on the Turkish language. There are nine competence components and 69 performance indicators in this area.

3. *Monitoring and Evaluation of Language Development* covers monitoring and evaluating students' Turkish language development. There are four competencies in this field and 27 performance indicators.

4. *The School, Family, and Community Cooperation* refers to collaboration with families about social leadership, school culture, ceremonies, and organizations to support Turkish teaching. There are five competencies and 27 performance indicators in this field.

5. *Professional Development in Turkish Lessons* covers professional development practices to support the Turkish lesson teaching process. There are three competencies in this field and 23 performance indicators (MoNE, 2008).

4.3 Competence Areas in the 2019 Turkish Lesson Curriculum

The desired skills in the 2019 Turkish Lesson Curriculum are covered under "competence areas." In other words, unlike other programs, the 2019 Turkish Lesson Curriculum described the competence areas in detail. The competencies are "operational components that facilitate the integration of our cultural heritage with humanity" (MoNE, 2019: 4). They are discussed in eight dimensions and shown in Figure 5:

Figure 6: The Competence Areas in 2019 Turkish Lesson Curriculum

As reported in the curriculum, digital competence refers to the safe and critical use of information communication technologies for business, daily life, and communication. This competence is supported by necessary skills such as access to information and the use of computers for the evaluation, storage, production, presentation, and exchange of information, as well as communication and participation in standard networks via the internet (MoNE, 2019: 5).

Learning to learn is one's ability to pursue and insist on learning opportunities within sufficient time and knowledge management to organize the learning process individually or collaboratively. This competence is characterized by the awareness of learning needs and available opportunities and coping with difficulties for successful learning (MoNE, 2019: 5).

Social and civic competencies include personal, interpersonal, and intercultural abilities, enabling individuals to effectively and constructively participate in society and working life, covering all forms of behaviors to resolve conflicts if required (MoNE, 2019: 5).

The sense of initiative and entrepreneurship stands for one's ability to put their thoughts into action. It involves creativity, innovation, taking risks, and planning and project management to achieve goals. This competence supports everyone at home and in the community, and business life to be aware of the context and conditions of their work and available job opportunities. It also includes awareness of ethical values and supports good governance" (MoNE, 2019: 5).

5. Conclusion and Discussion

In the Turkish Lesson Curriculum 2019, the most critical competence area is the "digital competence" dimension. We can see the reflections of digital competence in the definition of skills and educational text types. For example, reading skills in the program are dealt with to include screen and media reading comprehension beyond what is written on paper. Similarly, writing skill is defined beyond writing consistent texts on paper, and involves digital writing applications such as "blog," "e-mail," "social media messages." Besides, "information literacy, multiple literacies, digital literacy, e-book, technology literacy, and media literacy" are among the themes directly related to the digital competence in the curriculum.

The precondition for fostering digital competence in students is that teachers have digital competence. Thus, it is suggested to redefine and determine teaching competencies, knowledge, and skills related to "digital competence." Many studies in the literature emphasize the importance of digital competence. For instance, Geçgel, Kana, and Eren (2020: 899) indicated that "The texts in Turkish lesson coursebooks should both stimulate students' interest in digital competence and be suitable for technological changes. They stated that when students improve digital reading skills, it also contributes to improving digital literacy skills. Scherer, Siddiq, and Teo (2015) also stressed the significance of improving students' digital competence as the primary goal in the 21st century. According to Kurudayıoğlu and Soysal (2020: 186-187), digital competence is a natural result of our age's digitalization and technological developments. Today's people must be able to use digital media tools effectively.

"Learning to learn" another competence area discussed in the 2019 Turkish Lesson Curriculum, is one of the program's basic principles. The curriculum 2019 is based on the constructivism approach, and one of the most critical features of constructivism is to enable people to take responsibility for learning. Terminologically, the concepts such as "discovery teaching," "metacognitive learning," and "self-regulation" is associated with this learning principle. In brief, the Turkish Lesson Curriculum 2019 aims to make students strive to acquire knowledge and solve problems with patience and persistence. As Aydın (2015) stated, "learning to learn" is a paradigm based on structuring knowledge in a learning environment and reflects holistic learning properties such as learning by doing. Besides, 'learning to learn' encourages learners to integrate the available knowledge and skills with prior learning and life experiences and apply them in various contexts such as home, workplace, and educational settings (European Commission, 2007). In this sense, Demirel (2009: 701) suggests that the students of the information and technology age must have the essential skills of learning to learn, that is, the ability to rapidly access, evaluate and use the information from various sources.

"Social and civic competencies" is a field that regulates interpersonal relationships and promotes positive behavior patterns. Therefore, it can be stated that the most important goals of the curriculum are to develop problem-solving skills and make individuals a harmonious and effective component of social life. In addition, adaptation to different cultures and situations and developing practical communication skills can be considered within the scope of this competency area. In their studies, Aliyev and Öğmiş (2015: 54) found that people who appreciated the importance of intercultural interactions adapted more quickly to the new cultures and conditions than those who did not know others' cultural identity. Aslan and Arslan Cansever (2007) emphasize that individuals learn how to behave and cope with problems through the family's interactions, and the personality develops through identification, modeling, reinforcement, and learning.

"The sense of initiative and entrepreneurship" refers to individuals' life-oriented knowledge and skills. In this sense, it promotes recognizing and adapting to the available conditions and then evaluating the alternatives to exist and develop in given conditions. According to Pan and Akay (2015), entrepreneurship is one of the critical factors in increasing societies' development levels. They also emphasized that all societies want to raise influential entrepreneurs worldwide; therefore, entrepreneurship culture should be promoted in childhood. Yılmaz (2014: 305) stresses that entrepreneurship education is essential for the success of future ventures, for developing entrepreneurial behaviors among teenagers, and revealing their entrepreneurial potentials.

6. Implications

Teachers should be proficient in planning and implementing educational activities and assessment and evaluation procedures. Besides, they are expected to recognize students' needs and other variables such as timing, setting, and materials. They should acquire all of them during the undergraduate and in-service training (Gündoğdu, et al., 2015: 31).

The quality of education faculties should also be improved. The educational content should be determined considering the target audience's readiness and background. Therefore, students' readiness levels should be determined at the education faculties. The guidance of the lecturers and pre-service training are also essential factors for teacher candidates' experience.

The primary function of education faculties is to optimally prepare students with different readiness levels for the teaching profession. Students' different readiness, abilities, interests, and educational backgrounds should also be considered in their education. Thus, suitable educational settings should be prepared for all students to minimize the adverse effects of such differences (Altunçekiç, et al., 2005: 101).

The academic staff at universities should guide teacher candidates and provide them with real-life teaching experiences and educational settings that allow them to compensate for their lack of professional knowledge and experience, which in turn contribute to the proper functioning of the education system and to raise qualified individuals (Kahyaoğlu & Yangın, 2007: 84).

In conclusion, it is suggested to regularly review and update curriculums to train qualified teachers and improve prospective teachers' attitudes towards the teaching profession. Prospective teachers' expectations and needs should also be taken into account in this sense (Dönmez & Uslu, 2013: 13).

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